

Glucose Oxidase Immobilised in Polyurethane Matrix : A Biosensor for Amperometric Estimation of Glucose

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Manuscript received 3 February 1993

Glucose oxidase has been immobilised on platinum and carbon electrodes by physical entrapment through water induced polymerization of polyurethane (PU-6) prepolymers. The electrode thus prepared has been found to retain about 48% of enzyme activity compared to the native protein in solution. The enzyme electrode has been used for the *in vitro* estimation of glucose using amperometric method. Electron relays and mediators have been used to improve the performance of the glucose sensor. It has been observed that the combined use of relays and mediators improve the performance both in respect of sensitivity and working range of the electrode.

Biosensor is an analytical device which converts a biological signal produced by the interaction of the analyte (A) with the sensor into a quantifiable electrical signal¹. It usually consists of a biological component (B), interfaced with a transducer (T), which produces a signal on interaction with A (Fig. 1). The electrical signal so generated can

Fig. 1. A schematic representation of a biosensor : (A) analyte, (B) biological component which generates the signal, (I) interface, (T) transducer, (OS) output signal, (P) data processor and (O) output device.

be detected with or without further amplification (P, D). The choice of the transducer depends on the analyte/product of the biochemical reaction and/or the other biological components present in the analyte medium. The performance of a biosensor critically depends on appropriate interfacing of the biological component with transducer, which can be achieved in a number of ways²⁻⁶.

In order that the biological component can be

used repeatedly, without a major loss in its activity, it is essential that B is immobilised on a solid matrix such that it does not diffuse out in the analyte medium. The entrapment procedure should be simple and mild so that the biological component does not lose its activity. Further, the immobilisation matrix should be porous (to allow intimate contact between A and B) and should have a long life. The materials used should be relatively inexpensive. Chemical bonding helps in minimising leaching of biocatalyst from the matrix, but often induces changes in its conformation, thus resulting in lower enzyme activity. Physical entrapment normally preserves catalytic activity, but can lead to substantial leaching of the enzyme. The immobilising matrix is therefore has to be chosen with great care^{3,7} so as to minimise leaching while retaining activity of the enzyme. Entrapment in natural⁷ or synthetic polymer gels^{8,9} is one of the popular methods because of the relative ease in preparation and direct applicability to a variety of systems such as single- or multienzyme systems, organelles, cells etc. Polyurethane, a polyether diol of poly(ethylene glycol) and poly(propylene glycol) which is formed by the water-induced polymerization of its prepolymers, is one such gel. In the presence of water, the isocyanate functional groups at the terminal ends (Fig. 2) of the prepolymer form urea linkages with the liberation of carbon dioxide and resulting in polymerization^{8,10}. When

Fig. 2. The structure of polyurethane prepolymer. The relative ratios of a, b and c determine the hydrophobic or hydrophilic properties of the prepolymers.

prepolymers are mixed with an aqueous solution or aqueous suspension of the biocatalyst, gels are readily formed, entrapping the biocatalyst on a porous surface. Polyurethane prepolymer (PU-6) has a high content of poly(propylene glycol) (91%) and hence displays hydrophilic character. The hydrophobic properties of the prepolymer can be controlled by varying ratio of the poly(ethylene glycol) and the poly(propylene glycol) parts in the polyether diol moiety of the prepolymer.

One of the important biosensor from clinical view-point is the glucose sensor. This device has received wide attention^{11,12} and the sensors reported in the literature have met with mixed success. Some of the problems encountered are low electron transfer rates, nonlinearity of response, high cost and narrow range of applicability. The methods currently in vogue for the estimation of glucose in clinical samples depend on the use of glucose oxidase (GOD) which oxidises glucose to gluconic acid and hydrogen peroxide,

Redox reaction of glucose oxidase occurs in conjunction with a redox coenzyme, flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD). Glucose oxidase has an insulating glycoprotein envelope around the redox coenzyme, which hinders the transfer of electrons from the enzyme to the electrode surface¹³. It is possible to improve the electron transfer efficiency by introducing appropriate electron relays such as ferrocene or its derivatives^{2,13,14}. Also, soluble redox couples, such as potassium ferricyanide and quinhydrone, which are capable of diffusing readily from the solution to the enzyme and back, can serve the role of electron mediators for flavoenzymes¹⁵. In this paper, we report preparation of immobilised

GOD electrodes by physical entrapment in polyurethane matrix and the use of electron relays and mediators with a view to fabricate highly efficient glucose sensor.

Results and Discussion

Enzyme activity on polyurethane surface : The activity of GOD in aqueous solution was measured by standard methods¹⁶. The colouring compound *o*-dianisidine was dissolved in 0.1 M sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.2). The solution containing the enzyme was added to *o*-dianisidine solution along with peroxidase at 298 K. Glucose was added to the reaction mixture and the absorbance was measured after 10 min at 500 nm using a Spectronic 1201 spectrophotometer.

In the case of enzyme immobilised electrodes, the electrodes were dipped in the buffer containing *o*-dianisidine, peroxidase and the substrate. Measurements were done as explained above. It was found that immobilised enzyme retain 48% of the activity in solution. This is significantly higher than that reported for GOD immobilised with bovine serum albumin-glutaraldehyde matrix (where the activity retention has been reported to be 25 % of that in solution)^{17,18}. Thus, polyurethane proves to be a better immobilisation matrix.

Cyclic voltammetry : The redox properties of the immobilised enzyme electrode were determined by cyclic voltammetry, using a home-built equipment¹⁹. The immobilised enzyme electrode was used as the working electrode, saturated calomel electrode as the reference and platinum mesh as the counter electrode. A 0.1 M sodium phosphate solution (pH 6.8) was used as electrolyte. The potential was scanned from 0.0 to -0.8 V with a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ and current range of 1 mA. The

cyclic voltammogram of the immobilised glucose oxidase gave redox peaks at -0.57 and -0.63 V. These peaks correspond to the reduction and oxidation peaks of FAD. The negative shift of the redox peaks by 0.2 V when compared to those of native FAD in solution (redox potential is -0.4 V with respect to saturated calomel electrode) can be ascribed to the change in the environment around the redox center²⁰. But for this difference, the redox property of the enzyme remains unaltered on immobilisation.

Response of GOD electrodes to glucose : Electrochemical experiments were done with a three-electrode set-up. Saturated calomel electrode was used as reference and platinum electrode as the counter electrode. The working electrode (enzyme electrode), counter electrode and the reference electrode were kept in a glass cylinder. The lid had four inlets : three to insert the three electrodes and fourth for adding analyte solution (containing glucose) to the reaction cell. The reaction mixture was stirred gently and continuously with a magnetic stirrer. A constant potential was applied between the reference and working electrode using a dry cell. The current between the counter and the working electrode was measured with a digital multimeter of input impedance as high as $10\text{ M}\Omega$ (MECO, 45P, India, accuracy $\pm 0.75\%$).

The current generated between the working electrode and the counter electrode on addition of glucose was monitored with time. It is observed that the current increases linearly initially and levels off around 100 s. Therefore, we have made all subsequent measurements at the end of 120 s to ensure that the equilibrium condition has attained.

The response of the electrode over a range of glucose concentration (upto 15 mM) has been studied by measuring the current flowing through the circuit for different concentrations of glucose, at the end of 2 min in each case, after the insertion of the substrate into the electrochemical cell. The measurements have been done under different experimental conditions. Fig. 3 gives the plots of current in μA as a function of glucose concentration under different experimental conditions.

Fig. 3. Current as a function of glucose concentration for GOD immobilised in polyurethane matrix on platinum : (a) with mediator (0.6 mM potassium ferricyanide solution) (applied potential 0.36 V), (b) with relay (ferrocene) and without mediator (applied potential 0.8 V), (c) with mediator and relay (ferrocene) (applied potential 0.36 V) and (d) in the absence of both relay and mediator (applied potential 0.8 V); supporting electrolyte 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer, pH 6.8 , temperature 298 K . Other experimental details are described in the text.

Ferrocene and FAD are in close contact and help each other in electron transfer : Interfacing of the active center of the enzyme, FAD, with the electrode surface plays an important role in electron transfer kinetics. One of the ways in which the electron transport to and from the active center can be facilitated is by using an electron relay molecule, which can be introduced along with the enzyme during physical entrapment. We have used ferrocene as a relay for this purpose. As is seen from Fig. 3(b), ferrocene improves the electrode performance significantly in terms of the sensitivity of the electrode. Thus, ferrocene facilitates the transport of the electrons from the redox active site of glucose oxidase (i.e. FAD) by somehow shunting the glycoprotein envelope.

The improvement in the performance of enzyme electrodes containing ferrocene is likely to be related to a close interaction between ferrocene and the

coenzyme FAD. The proximity of the ferrocene (relay) to the FAD (electron donor) has been established by solid state ^{31}P nmr with magic angle spinning using a Bruker MSL 300 spectrometer. In GOD electrodes, two peaks appear at positions 11.91 and 10.93 ppm which can be assigned to the AMP and FMN phosphates belonging to the FAD-GOD. These peaks shift and merge into a single peak with a shoulder when ferrocene is incorporated, with the maximum at 11.75 ppm. Even though we do not fully understand the shunt mechanism, a change in the ^{31}P line profile indicates a close interaction between ferrocene and the phosphate moiety of FAD-GOD.

Mediators help in electron transport : The efficiency of a glucose sensor can be improved further by using mediators in the analyte solution. For example, Fig. 3(a) represents the electrode response in the presence of potassium ferricyanide in solution (0.6 mM) without any relay (ferrocene) in the matrix. This curve is only a small improvement over the behaviour of the enzyme electrode without mediators and the relays [Curve 3(d)]. Fig 3(b) represents a similar set of experiments without the mediator (ferricyanide) and with the relay in the matrix. Curve 3(c) is for the set where both the relay and the mediator were present simultaneously. From these sets of experiments, one can observe that the performance of the electrode is better when the simultaneous use of the relay and the mediator was done. It increases the linear range and sensitivity as can be seen from the Fig. 3. However, mediators are virtually ineffective in the absence of a relay.

Fig. 4 represents a comparative study for the performance of the electrode with relays in the matrix and the solution containing several different electron mediators. Curves (a), (b), (c) and (d) represent the experiments done with ferricyanide, chloropentamine cobalt(II) chloride, phenazine methosulphate and flavin mononucleotide in solution, respectively. One can observe from the slopes of the curves (given in the Table 1) that ferricyanide serves as a better electron mediator compared to the other substances studied. On the other hand FMN is least effective. The mediating efficiency

Fig. 4. Current as a function of glucose concentration for GOD immobilised in polyurethane matrix containing ferrocene on platinum : (a) with ferricyanide (0.6 mM, applied potential 0.36 V), (b) with chloropentaminecobalt(III) chloride (0.2 mM, applied potential 0.45 V), (c) with phenazine methosulphate (0.2 mM, applied potential 0.15 V), (d) flavin mononucleotide (0.2 mM, applied potential 0.25 V); supporting electrolyte 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer, pH 6.8, temperature 298 K. Other experimental details are described in the text.

of the electron shuttles follows the order : $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3+} > \text{PMS} > \text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}_3 > \text{FMN}$.

TABLE I—CHANGE IN CURRENT (μA) PER mM CONCENTRATION OF GLUCOSE FOR THE ENZYME ELECTRODE FOR VARIOUS ELECTRON MEDIATORS FOR THE PLATINUM AND CARBON BASED ENZYME ELECTRODES CONTAINING FERROCENE IN POLYURETHANE MATRIX

Solid support	change in current μA per mM			
	$\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}_3]$	PMS	FMN
Platinum	6.17	3.13	3.14	1.88
Carbon	3.92	2.48	2.65	1.51

Vitreous carbon is a good substitute for platinum : Conducting vitreous carbon sheets instead of platinum plates can be used as solid supports for preparing working electrodes. The response of this electrode for different electron mediators in solution with coimmobilised ferrocene is given in Fig. 5. One notices from the figure and the Table 1 that ferricyanide is better electron mediator and

Fig. 5. Current as a function of glucose concentration GOD immobilised in polyurethane matrix containing ferrocene on vitreous carbon : (a) with ferricyanide (0.6 mM, applied potential 0.36 V), (b) with chloropetammine-cobalt(III) chloride (0.2 mM, applied potential 0.45 V), (c) with phenazine methosulphate (0.2 mM, applied potential 0.15 V) and (d) flavin mononucleotide (0.2 mM, applied potential 0.25 V); supporting electrolyte 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer, pH 6.8, temperature 298 K. Other experimental details are described in the text.

FMN is least effective, consistent with the results obtained from platinum electrode. Similarly, electron mediators follow similar hierarchy as for platinum. These observations indicate that vitreous carbon-based electrode is equally efficient as platinum based ones. The effect of relays and mediators are similar in the two surfaces. However, the cost of vitreous carbon is much less and hence, it is advantageous to fabricate carbon-based electrodes.

Conclusions : Polyurethane is a better matrix for enzyme immobilisation as compared to the chemically crosslinked matrices. The process of immobilisation is mild and does not require difficult chemistry. Simultaneous use of relays and mediators remarkably improves the performance of the electrode with respect to the working range and the sensitivity. Our results indicate that less expensive vitreous carbon-based electrodes are equally efficient as expensive platinum based electrodes for fabricating

glucose sensors.

Experimental

Glucose oxidase (EC 1.1.3.4, type VII from *Aspergillus niger*) and horse raddish peroxidase (POD, EC1.1.11.7) were purchased from Sigma. Polyurethane prepolymer PU-6, a non-commercial product, was received as a gift (from Profs. A. Tanaka and K. Sonomoto, Kyoto University, Yoshida, Kyoto, Japan). All reagents used were of analytical grade or better.

Preparation of the enzyme electrode : Two surfaces were used for preparation of immobilised GOD electrodes : platinum (2.2 cm² sheet, annealed by heating and cleaned by washing with dilute nitric acid and water) and vitreous carbon (2.0 cm² sheet cleaned with ethanol and water). Aqueous solution of GOD (\approx 1000 units) was prepared in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer (pH 6.8: 200 μ l). The enzyme solution (100 μ l) was spread on one side of the strip along with the prepolymer PU-6 (\sim 5 mg) and allowed to polymerize (typically for 5–10 min). Immobilisation was repeated on the other side of the strip. The enzyme electrode thus formed was stored in dark overnight. The electrode was washed repeatedly with phosphate buffer and stored dry in dark. The washings were subjected to spectrophotometric detection to check the leaching of the enzyme and the washing was continued till no enzyme was detected in the washing. Incorporation of ferrocene was done by dispersing it thoroughly in enzyme solution and PU-6 before spreading it on the electrode surface, in order to achieve uniform distribution of ferrocene throughout the film. The average thickness of the enzyme immobilised matrix under dry conditions was 0.12 ± 0.02 mm.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the MSL nmr (300 MHz) facility at Bangalore for the solid state nmr experiments and to Profs. A. Tanaka and K. Sonomoto for their generous gift of polyurethane prepolymers. It is a pleasure to contribute this article in honour of Prof. S. Aditya, a distinguished chemist of our country.

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